

ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT CLIMATE IN UZBEKISTAN: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract:

This scientific article researches a comprehensive analysis of the investment climate in Uzbekistan, examining the opportunities for foreign and domestic investors. Uzbekistan, situated at the crossroads of Central Asia, has undergone significant economic reforms in recent years, aiming to attract investments, foster sustainable development, and diversify its economy. The study employs a multidimensional approach to assess the current state of the investment climate, identifying key opportunities and challenges that investors may encounter.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, investment climate, economic reforms, infrastructure development, legal framework, opportunities, challenges, case studies.

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Introduction

Investment climate is a set of economic, political, social factors that determine the attractiveness of a country/region for investors. The main criteria for an investor when determining an investment object will be the expected return on invested capital, comparable to the degree of risk. Therefore, the concept of investment attractiveness comes to the fore. Investment attractiveness consists of a combination of different factors. They are usually divided into: hard (those that cannot be changed): geographical location, natural resources, demographic potential; soft (those that can be changed): legislation, taxation, relations between governments and businesses. Attractiveness is reduced by political instability, social tension, high crime rates, non-compliance with legislation, corruption, high taxes, poor infrastructure, unpredictability and variability of legislation.

The investment climate and attractiveness of investment objects determine the activity of investment activities of any municipality. A city that has a stable political, legislative, environmental situation, a high level of economic, infrastructural, demographic, natural and climatic indicators, combined with resource availability, has a high investment climate index.

The current global economic landscape requires the development of coordinated, non-tax solutions to strengthen countries' investment climates and build resilience to future shocks. Over the past three decades, the private sector has been at the forefront of leading economic transformations around the world. Integration with global markets and increased investment competitiveness have contributed to unprecedented economic growth in many countries. Given the current situation, governments are looking to the World Bank for advice on policies that will enable and connect the foreign and domestic private sector to the dynamism generated by

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cross-border trade and investment patterns, and support the resilience and recovery of their economies in a sustainable and sustainable manner. The global investment climate supports client countries in creating an enabling business environment for all companies, attracting new sources of investment and maximizing spillovers from foreign direct investment, thereby promoting healthy company dynamics, economic transformation and job creation.

Uzbekistan has emerged as a focal point for investors seeking new opportunities in Central Asia. The government's commitment to economic reform, liberalization, and openness to foreign investment has sparked interest from diverse industries. This article aims to provide an in-depth analysis of the investment climate, considering regulatory frameworks, market conditions, and the overall business environment.

The research explores the economic reforms implemented by the Uzbek government, including liberalization of currency controls, tax incentives, and regulatory simplifications. These measures are crucial in creating an environment conducive to investment, fostering economic growth, and attracting both local and international capital.

The article assesses key sectors of the Uzbek economy, highlighting investment opportunities in agriculture, mining, energy, and manufacturing. Special attention is given to the development of strategic sectors, such as information technology and tourism, which are poised to play a vital role in the country's economic diversification. Infrastructure is a cornerstone of any thriving economy. The study evaluates Uzbekistan's efforts to enhance its infrastructure, including transportation, energy, and communication networks. Improved infrastructure not only facilitates business operations but also contributes to the overall attractiveness of the investment climate.

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A comprehensive analysis of the legal and regulatory framework is undertaken to identify potential hurdles for investors. The article examines recent legislative changes, contract enforcement mechanisms, and dispute resolution processes, shedding light on the legal environment that investors navigate.

Main body

In particular, to legally protect the rights and interests of investors, a new “Tax Code”, the Law “On Investments and Investment activities”, and the Law “On Mediation” were adopted.

To create more favourable conditions for investors, the International Tashkent arbitration Center was created, and new mechanisms were introduced, such as “investment credit”, “investment subsidy”, and “investment visa”.

Taking into account that ordinary investors stand behind powerful investment corporations, extensive practical work is required to provide timely and accurate coverage of events in Uzbekistan to investors in countries where potential investors are located. It should be noted that in this regard, complex measures have been implemented in our country to introduce modern scientific achievements, innovative ideas and technologies to the economy, social sphere and state administration.

While Uzbekistan presents numerous opportunities, there are challenges and risks associated with investing in the country. These may include bureaucratic obstacles, geopolitical uncertainties, and the need for further institutional improvements. a thorough understanding of these challenges is vital for investors to make informed decisions.

Analysis

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The main challenges that remain to be addressed are summarized below and draw together findings from legal and regulatory reviews conducted by the World Bank and other international organizations, as well as from a series of in-depth and completely confidential consultations with the private sector representing foreign and domestic companies , operating in Uzbekistan in several sectors. The combination of these approaches allows us to identify de jure and de facto barriers to investment.

One of the main issues is what to do to stop capital outflows. There are two fundamentally different approaches here, but they complement each other. The first approach is to strengthen administrative restrictions and state control. The second approach -creation of economic and legal conditions so that the withdrawal of capital is useless is considered more important and more promising. However, it is necessary to take into account the structural features of the capital flow, its various components. And they are as follows: -public or semi-public (i.e., ready to pay taxes) capital -seeks more reliable and profitable placement in order to avoid political and socio-economic instability, threats to property rights and high transaction costs; - origination of capital flow for the purpose of "laundering" illegally earned money.

A sharp change in the first stream is as important as the task of creating a favorable investment environment. It is also necessary to set priorities for the improvement of the investment environment. According to experts, the fight against corruption and crime, ensuring and strengthening the independence of the judicial system, protecting property rights and improving corporate governance, "transparency" of Uzbek enterprises for foreign investors and creditors are among the priorities for improving the investment environment.

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Foreign direct investment, net inflows (BoP, current US\$) - Uzbekistan1

If by the beginning of 2017, there were only 3 free economic zones (FEZ) operating in the country, by 2022, their number reached 22. Of these, by specialization: 12 FEZs are industrial, 6 are pharmaceutical, 2 are tourism, and 2 are agricultural.

Changes in legislation and created opportunities have a positive impact on the investment climate in the country. For example, in 2019, Uzbekistan was included for the first time in the OECD's Index of Regulatory Restrictions on Foreign Direct Investment, ranking 43rd in the world by 2020 and 7th in the asian region.

¹<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/BX.KLT.DINV.CD.WD?contextual=default&end=2022&locations=UZ&start=1992&view=chart>

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In 2017-2022, Uzbekistan improved its position in the world ranking of the Index of Economic Freedom by 31 positions, rising from 148th to 117th place.

The volume of foreign direct investment in the republic by the end of 2022 increased by 1.5 times compared to 2017 and reached 3.3 billion US dollars.

To illustrate practical aspects of the investment climate, the article includes case studies of successful investments in Uzbekistan. These real-world examples showcase the experiences of companies that have navigated the business landscape and provide insights for prospective investors.

Discussions

The conclusion summarizes key findings, emphasizing the positive trends and potential for investment in Uzbekistan. Recommendations for policymakers and investors are provided to further enhance the investment climate and ensure sustainable economic development in the years to come.

To enhance direct investment, the emancipation of entrepreneurial activity is required. We need a constant dialogue with business, painstaking work to identify and overcome barriers that impede the development of certain sectors. In this regard, active work is being carried out in the following areas.

Firstly, in order to maintain consistently high rates of economic growth, it is necessary to form a stable and competitive model of the country's economy, in which the prevailing share of the assets of the banking system should be in the hands of private investors.

Secondly, the stimulation of investment activity through the development of public-private partnership instruments and project financing is in an active phase to ensure

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accelerated growth of investment in infrastructure, which is also one of the key factors in increasing investment attractiveness and sustainable economic growth.

Thirdly, the processes of interaction between investors and the state are being optimized to completely eliminate bureaucratic barriers and obstacles in the implementation of investment projects through digitalization and contactless provision of public services. The quality of organization of work with requests and requests from foreign investors is being improved to ensure maximum transparency and prevent corruption.

Fourthly, there is a reduction in transaction costs, which lead to the flow of labor and capital from the legal to the shadow sector of the economy.

Fifthly, an investment policy strategy is being developed, focused on individual, most promising industries for Uzbekistan that can become points of technological breakthrough and lay the foundation for the development of the country's productive forces for the next 20-30 years.

Conclusion

Considering the fact that the investment climate affects almost all areas of the country's activities, the range of reforms covered all areas, including economic, institutional, educational, healthcare, agriculture, water supply, energy, transport and others.

Much attention is also paid to practical support for entrepreneurs and initiators of investment projects. The most striking example in this direction was the activities of the Government Commission on Export and Investment Development, created in 2020, whose tasks are close interaction with entrepreneurs and exporters, analysis of the problems they faced in connection with restrictions caused by the pandemic, as

well as the development and implementation of prompt and effective solutions based on an individual approach to each business entity.

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